

Loss of Consciousness Caused by a Rare Etiology: *Serratia Marcescens* Endocarditis

Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Serratia marcescens* is an uncommon cause of infective endocarditis and is associated with a rapidly progressive clinical course, early embolic complications, and high mortality. Its initial presentation with neurological symptoms rather than cardiac manifestations is particularly rare and frequently contributes to diagnostic delay.

Case Presentation: We report a 46-year-old male with multiple coagulation factor deficiencies undergoing intermittent hemodialysis via a subclavian catheter. Following non-sterile self-removal of his catheter, he presented to the emergency department with acute onset neck pain, altered mental status, and elevated inflammatory markers. Brain diffusion MRI revealed multiple lacunar infarcts initially attributed to minor cerebrovascular disease. Despite empiric broad-spectrum antimicrobial therapy, the patient's neurological condition rapidly deteriorated. Blood cultures subsequently grew *S. marcescens*, and echocardiography performed on day 10 demonstrated a mitral valve vegetation consistent with infective endocarditis. Surgical intervention was deemed unsuitable due to the severity of clinical deterioration. The patient developed multiorgan failure and died on the 14th day of hospitalization.

Discussion: This case highlights the aggressive nature of *S. marcescens* endocarditis, its strong association with catheter-related bloodstream infections, and its tendency to mimic primary neurological disease through early cerebral embolization. Biofilm-associated antimicrobial resistance likely contributed to treatment failure despite broad-spectrum therapy. Early integration of neurological findings, catheter history, and rising troponin levels is vital for timely diagnosis.

Conclusion: *S. marcescens* endocarditis should be considered in patients presenting with unexplained altered mental status and a history of recent catheter manipulation. Prompt microbiological investigation and early echocardiographic assessment are essential for managing this high-mortality condition.

Keywords: *Serratia marcescens*; Infective endocarditis; Neurological complications

Introduction

Serratia marcescens is a gram-negative, motile bacterium recognized as an opportunistic pathogen, particularly in

healthcare-associated infections. While it most frequently causes respiratory and urinary tract infections, it may rarely lead to severe systemic infections, including

meningitis, sepsis, and infective endocarditis. Endocarditis caused by *S. marcescens* is characterized by a fulminant clinical course, frequent embolic complications, multiorgan involvement, and prominent neurological manifestations such as altered mental status (1). Despite appropriate antimicrobial therapy, reported mortality rates remain high, underscoring the need for early recognition.

Herein, we present a fatal case of *S. marcescens* endocarditis presenting primarily with neurological symptoms and altered mental status.

Case Report

A 46-year-old male with known deficiencies of coagulation factors II, VII, IX, and X was receiving intravenous factor replacement therapy and intermittent hemodialysis via a subclavian catheter. Approximately one week prior to admission, the patient performed a non-sterile self-removal of his vascular catheter at home.

The day before presentation, he developed nocturnal nausea and experienced a brief episode of loss of consciousness the following morning. Upon arrival at the emergency department, he complained of acute neck pain.

Vital signs on admission were: blood pressure 110/60 mmHg, heart rate 130/min, oxygen saturation 97%, and body temperature 36.8°C.

Initial laboratory evaluation revealed elevated inflammatory markers and increased troponin levels. Brain diffusion-weighted MRI demonstrated multiple lacunar infarcts. During follow-up, the patient developed rapidly progressive deterioration in consciousness and

disorientation—findings disproportionate to the extent of the lacunar infarctions. With a preliminary diagnosis of meningitis or encephalitis, blood cultures were obtained, and empiric meropenem therapy was initiated. The patient was admitted to the intensive care unit.

On hospital day 3, blood cultures grew *S. marcescens*. Despite broad-spectrum antimicrobial therapy, the patient's condition continued to worsen. On hospital day 10, transthoracic echocardiography revealed a mitral valve vegetation consistent with infective endocarditis. Surgical intervention was deemed inappropriate due to severe clinical status. The patient subsequently developed multiorgan failure and died on hospital day 14.

Discussions

Serratia marcescens is a well-recognized opportunistic pathogen; however, its role as an etiologic agent of infective endocarditis remains exceedingly rare (1,2). Despite its low incidence, *S. marcescens* endocarditis is associated with a fulminant clinical course and markedly high mortality (1,3). The present case is notable because the initial presentation was dominated by neurological symptoms rather than classical cardiac findings, contributing to diagnostic delay (1,4).

Previous reports indicate that *S. marcescens* endocarditis most often arises following catheter-related bloodstream infections, predominantly affects left-sided valves, and is frequently complicated by early cerebral embolization (1,2). In our patient, diffusion MRI demonstrated multiple lacunar infarcts consistent with septic emboli. A distinctive feature was the patient's self-removal of the vascular catheter, which likely precipitated bacteremia. Catheter manipulation is a well-established risk factor, particularly for biofilm-forming organisms like *S.*

marcescens (4). Biofilm formation contributes to antimicrobial resistance, potentially explaining the lack of clinical response despite broad-spectrum therapy (3,4).

Although *S. marcescens* endocarditis is rare, it shares clinical characteristics with other atypical etiologies. Non-HACEK gram-negative bacilli (e.g., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and fungal pathogens, especially in healthcare-associated settings, are strongly associated with intravascular devices and exhibit a more aggressive course compared to classical pathogens (5). In such cases, central nervous system involvement often occurs early, and neurological manifestations may precede cardiac symptoms. Accordingly, in patients with a history of vascular catheterization who fail to improve despite therapy, infective endocarditis caused by rare pathogens should be strongly considered, and early echocardiographic evaluation is warranted.

Conclusion

This case underscores that *S. marcescens* endocarditis, though rare, is an aggressive infection prone to delayed diagnosis and rapid progression. Early echocardiographic assessment combined with targeted microbiological evaluation is crucial in patients presenting with neurological symptoms and a history of catheter manipulation.

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